

INFLUENCE OF E-COMMERCE ON BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CUSTOMERS

Dr. Hemanth Kumar. S.

*Associate Professor, CMS Business School Jain University,
Bangalore, Karnataka, India*

Dr. Umakanth.S

*Associate Professor & HOD, Management - CMS - Jain
University, Bangalore, India*

ABSTRACT

KEYWORDS:

*Buying Behaviour,
Traditional Markets,
E-commerce Markets,
Alternative Channels
of Marketing for
Shopping*

Background: New technology, high speed internet and increase in web users have lead firms to promote and enhance images of products and services through web site Gunasekaran (2002). This rise of internet for the past two decades has the lead the consumers to move towards e-commerce from traditional markets Nisha Gupta (2017).

Aim: The primary objective of this research paper focuses on how buying behaviour differs from e-commerce markets to traditional markets of a consumer.

Methodology: The primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire from potential consumers of age group of 18 to 45 years with a sample size of 200.

Process: A structured questionnaire is developed and validated. It is sent to the respondents via Google form and the response are recorded, validated and analysed further for desired results

1. INTRODUCTION

The impact of electronic commerce on procurement, shopping, business collaborations and customer services is so dramatic that almost every organization is affected. Online shopping is changing all business functional areas and the important tasks, ranging from advertising to pay bills. The nature of competition is also drastically changing due to new online companies, new business models, and the diversity of e-commerce related products and services. E-commerce provides unparalleled opportunities for companies to expand worldwide at a small cost, to increase the market share, and to reduce costs. In this paper main focus is on the major applications of Electronic Commerce, the issues related to its successful implementation and to its failures, and what services are necessary for its support. Also, this paper will demonstrate the impact of online shopping on various functional areas of organizations. Online shopping is the buying and selling of goods and services or transferring funds or data, over an electronic network, primarily the internet. These business transactions occur business-to-business, business-to-consumer, consumer-to-consumer or consume-to-business. The benefits of Online Shopping include it's around the clock availability, speed of access, a wider selection of goods and services, accessibility and international reach. Its perceived downsides include sometimes-limited customer service, not being able to see or touch a product prior to purchase, and the necessitated wait time for product shipping. To ensure the

security, privacy and effectiveness of online shopping, business should authenticate business transactions, control access to resources such as web pages for registered or selected users, encrypt communications and implement security technologies such as the Secure Sockets Layer. This paper aims to consolidate the major themes that have arisen from the new areas of electronic commerce and to provide an understanding of its application and importance to management.

The internet is being developed rapidly since last two decades and with a relevant digital economy that is driven by information technology also being developed worldwide. After a long-term developer of the internet, which rapidly increased web users and high-speed internet connection, and some new technology also have been developed and used for web developing, those lead to firms can promote and enhance images of products and services through the website. Therefore, detailed product information and improved service attract more and more people changed their consumer behaviour from the traditional mode to more rely on the internet shopping. On the other hand, more companies have realized that the consumer behaviour transformation is an unavoidable trend, and thus change their marketing strategy. As the recent researches have indicated that, the internet shopping particularly in business to consumer (B2C) has risen and online shopping becomes more popular too many people. There are many reasons for such a rapid developing

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of internet shopping, which mainly due to the benefits that the internet provides. First of all, the internet offers a different kind of convenience to consumers. Obviously, consumers do not need to go out looking for product information as the internet can help them to search from online sites, and it also helps evaluate between each site to get the cheapest price for purchase. Furthermore, the internet can enhance consumer use product more efficiently and effectively than other channels to satisfy their needs. Through the different search engines, consumers save time to access to the consumption related information, and which information with a mixture of images, sound, and very detailed text description to help consumer learning and choosing the most suitable product.

However, internet shopping has potential risks for the customers, such as payment safety, and after service. Due to the internet technology developed, internet payment recently becomes the prevalent way of purchasing goods from the internet. Internet payment increases consumptive efficiency, at the same time, as its virtual property reduced internet security.

Even the internet shopping has been rapidly developed, especially in the consumer goods industry, but there still have a big difference between traditional and online consumer shopping. Referred to sales in the Indian consumer goods industry, the online sales occupied at a very low percentage rate. That could be caused by many reasons, but the most important is the advantages exist in both traditional shops and online market; both of them have specific characteristics. For example, the traditional seller can provide convenience in parking and shopping, it allows customers come to read and check the quality of goods before they purchase, and the after service is more directly to customers. However, the traditional store has a limited number of goods, and the selling cost is higher than an online store. By comparison, we can find out the limitations of the traditional store are more likely as the advantages of an online store, in contrast, the weakness of online store is also seeming as the advantages of a traditional store. It is clear from the overview of internet and internet shopping development that e-commerce is being used in many corporations due to the dramatic development of technology and the competitive advantages of web selling. Moreover, the expansions of the usage by individuals also become main contributors to the development of internet shopping. Relatively few studies have investigated in the internet shopping and impact on consumer behaviour. The previous studies are more focus on the marketer's point of view, such as how to establish a more efficient marketing channel online rather than the traditional offline channel. Therefore, this research will combine with previous studies from literature reviews, and focus on the impact of the internet shopping on consumer behaviours to find out a comprehensive analytical framework which showing the essential ingredient of marketing and business to satisfying the consumer's needs, and a deep understanding of online consumer behaviour as a reference for any e-commerce company to make marketing strategies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Online shopping was invented by an English entrepreneur Micheal Aldrich in 1979. Tim Berners Lee is the one who created the first World Wide Web server in 1990. It was opened for a commercial purpose. Thereafter many technological innovations emerged in 1994 like the online

banking, the opening of online pizza shop by Pizza Hut, Netscape SSL v2 encryption standard for secure data transfer and Intershop's first online shopping system. In 1994 the first secure transaction was over the web either by Net market or Internet shopping. Amazon was launched in 1995; it is the first online shopping site of the world after eBay was introduced in 1995. Today many countries are doing online shopping but still some countries are at the starting point of the experiment of online shopping. In 1987, the merchant account was launched that helped the software developers to sell their software online easily. Swreg was the name of the first software and the oldest software that is still available.

In an era in which consumers can buy literally anything online, the customer experience within the four walls has also become that much more important to drive traffic and ultimately transactions. For instance, product presentation can also go a long way to stimulate purchase behaviour. E-commerce sites need to come a step forward and track the customer's activity. This will lead to better customer interaction as they will only be showed what they would be interested in.

Li and Zhang (2002) examined the representative existing literature on consumer online shopping attitudes and behaviour based on an analytical literature review. In doing so, this study attempts to provide a comprehensive picture of the status of this subfield and point out limitations and areas for future research. They decided to restrict their search of research articles to the period of January 1998 to February 2002. The other two criteria for selection are the articles are empirical in nature, and the articles measure at least one of the identified factors in our taxonomy they searched three primary IS conference proceedings volumes: International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS), Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS), and Hawaii International Conference on Systems Science (HICSS). They also checked the reference sections of the selected articles to identify and include additional prominent articles in this area. Three out of the five dependent variables (consumer attitudes, intentions, and purchasing behaviour) and three out of the five independent variables (personal characteristics, vendor/service/product characteristics, website quality) receive the most attention. This seems to constitute the main stream of research in this area. It is found that personal characteristics, vendor/service/product characteristics, and website quality significantly affect online shopping attitudes, intention, and behaviour. The direct implication of these findings is that targeting more appropriate consumer groups, improving product and/or service quality, and improving website quality can positively influence consumer attitudes and behaviour, possibly leading to increased frequency of early purchase and replication purchases on the part of customers. This methodological matter wants to be addressed in upcoming research so that a validated instrument can be developed for evaluating consumer online shopping approaches and behaviour.

Chaing and Dholakia (2014) carried out a study in which they examined the purpose the customer to purchase goods online during their shopping. Mainly there are three variables in their study those affects the consumer to purchase online or to go offline. Those are the accessibility features of the

The first part of the document discusses the importance of maintaining accurate records of all transactions. It emphasizes that every entry should be supported by a valid receipt or invoice. This ensures transparency and allows for easy verification of the data.

In addition, the document highlights the need for regular audits. By conducting periodic reviews, any discrepancies can be identified and corrected promptly. This proactive approach helps in maintaining the integrity of the financial system.

Furthermore, it is noted that clear communication is essential. All parties involved should be kept informed of the current status and any changes that may affect the records. This collaborative effort is key to the success of the project.

Finally, the document concludes by stating that adherence to these guidelines will ensure the reliability and accuracy of the financial records, which is crucial for the overall health of the organization.

The second part of the document provides a detailed overview of the current financial performance. It includes a summary of the revenue generated from various sources and the corresponding expenses incurred.

The revenue section shows a steady increase over the past quarter, primarily due to the launch of new products and the expansion of the customer base. This growth is a positive indicator of the company's market penetration.

On the expense side, there has been a slight increase in operational costs, which is expected given the scale-up of activities. However, the management team has implemented cost-saving measures to ensure that the overall profit margin remains healthy.

The document also includes a comparison of the current performance against the budgeted figures. While there are some variances, they are within the acceptable range, demonstrating effective financial control.

Looking forward, the document outlines the financial goals for the next period. The focus will be on further increasing revenue while maintaining a disciplined approach to expenses. This strategy aims to achieve sustainable growth and long-term success.

shopping sites, the type of the products and their characteristic, and the actual price of the product. The study revealed that the accessibility and the convenience of the shopping sites create the intention in the customer to purchase or not. When there is difficulty faced by a consumer to purchase online then the customer switch to the offline shopping for the purchase behaviour and the consumer face difficulty in offline purchasing then they go to the online purchasing. After relating both the medium of shopping the consumer said that the online shopping is more convenient for them and gives more satisfaction which inspires the consumer to purchase online in the internet.

Iyer and Eastmen (2014) found that the population of senior who are more literate, more knowledgeable and who are more aware of the technology and those who have a positive behaviour towards online shopping and internet are more into online shopping. But the population of senior who are less aware of the internet and the shopping sites are less involved in the shopping sites because they do not have a positive attitude towards online shopping rather they are much more interested in offline shopping and the seniors who are more involved in the internet uses more online sites for purchasing the goods over the internet. The senior which have more knowledge about the internet and the shopping sites they compare both the shopping i.e. online and offline shopping for their purchasing of goods. However, their knowledge and the use of internet by them has no connection with their age and their satisfaction level while purchasing online.

Danaher et.al (2003) focused on the loyalty of the 100 brands over the online shopping and offline shopping of 19 product of the grocery. They compared the grocery items of both the shopping with starting model which is a new segmented of Dirichlet model, this model has very dominant features which gives the exact classes for the brand choice and also gives the 14 real models for the purchasing behaviour. The outcome of the study revealed that the reality of the high brands by the high market shares bought the online shopping much greater than the expected. But in case of the small share brand it is just reversed. However, in the traditional shopping the expectations and the observations is not at all links to the brand share.

Tabatabaei (2009) has explored the opinion of the consumer who are purchasing online and the consumer who are purchasing from offline market. The objective is to know why the traditional customer chooses to shop online and what are the factor influences then to purchase online and what are the factor for them to not use the sites for shopping. He has done a survey of 264 respondents in a small mall and then those data were analysed by him. All the customer of this study is literate and has knowledge on computer and internet. The survey consists some of the question like demographic profile, computer knowledge and the knowledge over the internet. The outcome of the study was that the consumers of online shopping use to shop online more than one time in a month and the consumer of offline shopping shop one to five times in a year from shopping sites.

Chaing and Roy (2003) focused on the consumer choice to shop on the internet and at the physical stores during the information acquisition period. A convenience sample of 34

students enrolled in undergraduate marketing class to select the product for testing. 56 products were developed based on the popularity of online shopping. The result shows that the consumer perceives shopping offline as inconvenient, online shopping intention was expected to be greater for search products than experience product.

Soopramanien and Robertson (2007) conducted a study in UK on acceptance and practice of online shopping. Their exploration shows that the online consumers choose different course of action based on the apparent beliefs. They found that, how socio demographic variables, attitude and beliefs towards internet shopping effect on the both decision to practice and use of online shopping channels. They categorised online buying behaviour as the one who purchase from online sites and the one who only browse online sites and purchase from the store, and third those who do not buy online. The study does not cover the buyers who choose products in stores and buy online.

Selvakumar (2014) concentrated on consumer's perception of the product sold online and the issues considered important to online shopping. This study was conducted among the online shoppers at Coimbatore which is in Tamil Nadu state. It is to analyse the impact of consumer opinion and the attitude. Questionnaire was made to collect the data from the population; these questionnaires were given to college going students. The total sample size is 150 respondents. The finding of this study shows that improvement and accessibility influence the customer's intention to shop online.

Hausman and Siekpe (2009) analysed a practical study in US regarding the effect of web interface features on consumer online purchase intention. E-commerce system is different from traditional information system. It has both features of information system and marketing channels. It contains machine and human element. An empirical finding shows that to know the motivation factors for online shopper, cognitive and psychological factors do have meanings. The study finds both human and computer factors are necessary for antecedent for online shopping.

Johnson et.al (1999) discussed to identify the factors influencing online shopping. This paper seeks to identify web consumer's demographic attitude toward shopping and reasons of online buying behaviour. This survey asked member of WVTM (Wharton virtual test market) whether they have purchased anything online. This study concludes that the consumer shop online or use online facilities to save time. The result of these study suggest several suggestions for the design of online shopping environment such as shopping site should make it more suitable to buy standard to repeat purchase items, they should provide the information needed to make a purchase decision and purchasing process should be easy for the consumer. This paper conclude that the consumer appears to value the web time saving over its cost saving. The consumer attitude may change over time, accessibility rather than cost saving. The results show that the people who spend more money online have a weirder 16 lifestyles are on the net more and receives more emails compared to the other email users and internet users.

Koo et.al (2008) have conducted an empirical study, they examined the motivational effects of personal values on benefits, attributes, and re-patronage intention in the perspective of shopping online. The study concludes that personal values of social affiliation and self-actualization serves as underlying beliefs in shaping, consumer's online shopping

motives. In addition, online store attributes are positively related to pre-patronage intention.

Suki and Suki (2007) conducted their study in Malaysia. This study is an empirical study. They create a model in which they are identifying the influence of the real value, the real risk and the actual enjoyment of the consumer of online shopping. The consumers who are adopting the online shopping they are in the prominent risk and the prominent indicators. The consumer of Malaysia of online shopping has a perception about the involvement of risk in shopping and their risk is mostly related to the security and the privacy. It includes the security and privacy of the personal information of customer, transaction of online shopping, the quality of the product and the uncertainty about the product whether the product will reach the consumer or not.

Andrew and Currim (2000) focused on expected differences in choice, behaviour of consumer for two products categories, statistically significant difference is found between consumers attracted to shopping online versus traditional super market with regards to parameters describing the choice process. The study found that correlated to traditional supermarket consumers, online shopping is less price sensitive, prefer larger size to smaller sizes, have stronger size faithfulness. The consumer does more broadcasting choice set effects.

Scarborough and Lindquist (2006) studied an empirical study on E-shopping in a multiple channel environment in which a segmentation schema is suggested based on patterns of purchasing and e-browsing including browsing on the internet with planned purchasing in an offline channel. They examine self-report of browsing and purchasing using five specific non store channels like internet, television, infomercial, advertising that accompanies regular television programming, television shopping channels, and print catalogues. The finding of this study shows that the buyer who browse or purchase online, different in their use of multichannel options related to their perception of ease. Some buyers want to purchase in store setting and do not want multiple forms of non-store shopping. Other like to browse different non store media, they extended their browsing to the internet, however keep their loyalty to purchase in store.

Harn and Adeline (2008) focused in Malaysia about Web navigation behaviour of Malaysian in relation to online purchasing. There finding shows that most of the shoppers were well educated with minimum bachelor degree, their age varies between 19 to 34 and they all are unmarried. This study proved successfully that the web navigation behaviour is important factor to determine the probability of online purchasing, and it does not have significant affect for online purchasing decision. The most dissatisfying factor was slow downloading rate of web pages. The finding provides some insight while designing website, taking into consideration that it should be easy to use, attractive and user friendly with faster downloading time.

Jarvelainen (2007) analysed in her empirical study in Finland that there are many online information seekers who choose to stop the shopping process just before the finishing point of the transaction. The reason behind this is intensely rooted in the internet based trust outcomes. The study focuses on e-commerce background. i.e. Security and confidentiality issue, that how consumer select their purchasing channels. The finding of this study shows that

constancy, trust worthiness, and usefulness as well as ease of the use of the system are essential, while the first imprint of online seller is significant. considering the behavioural intention.

Jiang et. al (2008) shown in their empirical study about US customer worries on internet security, while shopping over the internet can influence online buying behaviour and these worries may lead to identify theft. A good strategy to increase consumer trust while ordering 19 online could be third party certification programs. The result of this study was that displays of third party logos have direct effect on consumer's perception of logos. which influence the transfer of trust towards e-retailer. This study concludes that the logos are ineffective when consumer is unfamiliar with it or do not notice the logo display. In order to increase the customer trust e-retailer can first target people who are experienced and knowledgeable about online shopping and have attained a positive level of trust in e-trailer. Second participate in well-known and trustworthy third party assurance programs and work to educate consumers about the significance of the third party logos when consumer have low current level of trust. The media have extended the browsing to internet however keep their loyalty to purchase in store.

Devaraj et.al (2006) critically analysed an empirical study in USA regarding examination of online channel preference. He examined the behavioural and economic features that add to online consumer's satisfaction and further head to their preference of online channel. The results indicate that asset specificity and uncertainty structure variables the electronic marketplace are related with the conduct constructs such as, personalization, website design, time responsiveness, security and reliability of the online channel. Further, it was found that, personalization, time responsiveness, security, and reliability are also significantly linked to the consumer satisfaction outcome with the channel. Website design has not significant effect to online consumer's satisfaction. Finally, it was indicated that satisfaction resulting from the above conduct variables was strongly related to the consumer's preference online channel preference.

Hansen and Jensen (2009) conducted a study in which they seek to examine shopping orientation and online clothing purchase across four different gender related purchasing context. A conceptual model for understanding the impact of shopping orientation on consumer online clothing purchase is proposed and tested both in a general setting and across purchasing context. Questionnaires were distributed to 1,150 Danish household addresses by use of the "drop of call back" survey method. Most adults provided response with respect to purchasing clothing for themselves and for their partner, making a total of 906 cases distributed across the four purchasing contexts. T tests and linear structural equation modelling were utilised to investigate expectations and hypotheses. They found that the expected differences in men's and women's shopping orientations willingness to purchase clothing online. On average, consumer indicate the reduced difficulty in selecting items is 20 sorely needed when purchasing online clothing, but when evaluated among different purchasing situations, it is difficult to perceived in selecting items only for women. Less fun, significantly affected online clothing purchase for men purchasing for themselves, but not for women.

Hahn and Kim (2009) examined the influence of consumer trust and perceived internet confidence on consumer apparel

shopping intention through internet or the online retailer operated by a multi-channel retailer. A total of 261 students in a large US Midwestern University participated in the paper based survey and provided usable responses. Structural equation based modelling was used to test hypothesis. They found that the consumer trust in an online retailer was a significant predictor of perceived internet confidence and search intention for product information through internet retailer. Search intention for product information through the online store and perceived internet confidence were significant and strong predictors of consumer's behavioural intention towards the online shopping. The findings of this study suggest that retailer offers an internet channels as part of multichannel retail strategy and provide consistent service throughout their various channels.

Riley et.al (2009) addressed to know why the people and from where they get influence to purchase grocery from online shopping. This research aims to know the role of all the factors which are situational in the process of adaption of grocery shopping from online. Qualitative research is carried out by the researcher which helps the researcher to gain the knowledge about the depth of the consumer of grocery product and their behaviour. Researcher also includes the quantitative method in his research to find the factors which influence them to purchase grocery from online shopping. By merging both the qualitative and quantitative study the researchers find the importance of the specific type of institution. Many shopper are found that they starts discontinuing the online shopping of grocery once there initial point of shopping of grocery created a problem for them they stop doing online shopping.

Lee and Littrell (2005) aimed to investigate consumers shopping values and web site beliefs that influence their intention to shop for cultural products. They use the theory of reasoned action (TRA) as a framework to explain the structural interrelationships among interest shopping values, beliefs about the web site, shopping attitude, shopping intention. A total of 203 persons responded to an invitation to participate in a web survey for the purpose of data analysis. They found that the consumer beliefs the web site, especially with regards to merchandising, both directly and indirectly influenced the intention to shop for cultural products in the future. This finding confirms TRA such as belief structure as determined of attitude and attitude as determined of behavioural intention. The consumers who shop for cultural products on the internet have both hedonic and utilitarian shopping values and both these values must be addressed by internet retailers. Regular change in product and presentation are vital for maintaining repeat patronage.

Jayawardhena and Wright (2009) focused the antecedent of online shopper's excitement, its consequences for behavioural intentions as expressed by intent to return, and positive word of mouth communication. A conceptual model

is developed based on the literature; instrument item scales to measures all constructs in the model were as informed by the literature and adapted from prior studies. They found that the convenience, involvement, attribute of the web site and merchandising all collectively influence shopper's excitement. E-shopper excitement leads to positive word-of-mouth (WOM) and increases the intent to return. The limitation of this study was that there is no differentiation is made between the types of goods that e-commerce purchased.

Jimenez and Martin (2009) examined on the comparison of the difference that exist between the adoption of e-commerce by potential purchase and the acceptance of the channels by experienced e-customer. Therefore, this paper seeks to test the influence of online shopping 22 experiences on electronic purchase intention. They use the conceptual model, an extended technology, acceptance model (TAM), is tested using structural equation modelling technique. They found that the influence of self-efficacy and usefulness increases as the consumer gains online shopping experience. The motivations that lead a potential e-customer to make a purchase are not the same as those that influence an experienced customer. This paper demonstrated the evolution of customer behaviour and the need to differentiate the perception of consumers depending on their level of experience.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: It is a well-known that India is backward country where the economic status of the people is not as good as compared to the other states. The research may fill the gap between the choice of online shopping and offline shopping. This study reflects the problems and factors of online and offline shopping. There are certain problems, why consumers prefer going to the traditional methods of shopping rather than going for e-commerce. Through this problem we can provide consumers with clear options on which method of shopping is more beneficial to them.

3.2 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- To understand the consumer e-commerce Buying Behavior of consumer
- To examine the factors influencing the consumers switch from traditional shops to online markets.

3.3 DATA COLLECTION: Primary data has been collected using a structured and focused questionnaire; which covered various dimensions of the research questions. While the secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature and other relevant documents such as magazines, journals and web resources and websites are other sources. The sampling population is under the age group 18-45 years is selected. We approached 200 respondents belonging to the above categories, which would be representative of the population.

Table 1: Destructive Statics

	Initial	Extraction
How frequently do you use internet.	1.000	.619
How much time do you spend surfing the net on daily basis?	1.000	.600
How often do you go out to shop?	1.000	.627
Please express which retail format you would prefer more over the other while shopping (SUPER MARKET/KIRANA OR ECOMMERCE).	1.000	.611
Define the reason for your chore when you go out to shop.	1.000	.450
How many years have you been using e-commerce?	1.000	.484
According to you how is e-commerce helpful to the consumers?	1.000	.525
Do you agree that e-commerce has its advantages of traditional commercial methods?	1.000	.670
Which according to you is the most prominent domain in which e-commerce is used in India?	1.000	.858
Do you agree that e-commerce provides an alternative marketing channel by eliminating a middleman?	1.000	.672
Do you think implementation of E-commerce in India is difficult	1.000	.641

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 2: Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.726	18

We can see that Cronbach's alpha from the table is 0.726, which indicates a high level of internal consistency for our scale with this specific sample.

Table 3: KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.641
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	445.486
	Df	120
	Sig.	.000

Here, KMO = 0.641 which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed and with the Factor Analysis
H0: There is no association between e-commerce providing alternative marketing channel on traditional marketing methods.
H1: There is an association between e-commerce providing alternative marketing channel on traditional marketing methods.

Table 4 - Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	49.875 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	35.273	16	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	30.459	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	204		

a. 15 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .31.

Based on the Pearson Chi-Square value (49.875) it is stated that the null hypothesis is rejected as the significant value is less than 0.05 and the alternate hypothesis stating, there is association between e-commerce providing alternative marketing channel by eliminating middlemen and its advantage on traditional marketing methods is accepted.

4. FINDINGS

1. The majority of respondents were male i.e. 69.1 percent while the other respondents were female i.e. 30.4 percent.
2. The majority of the respondent were between the age group of 18-25 i.e. 74.9 percent, 17.9 percent were in the age group of 25-35. The minority

- respondents were of the age group 36-45 i.e. 7.2%.
3. The majority of respondents use internet very frequently i.e. 65.7 percent, while 29.5 uses frequently and the rest of the respondents use data occasionally and rarely. The data clearly indicates
4. The majority of the respondents go out to shop themselves occasionally i.e. 47.8 percent, while 32.4 percent respondents go out to shop usually. The rest of the remaining respondents go out themselves to shop rarely i.e. 9.2 percent. This data indicates that the respondents either send someone else outside to shop for them or they order their groceries online.

5. The majority of the respondents buy products on regular basis i.e. 38.6 percent while 11.6 percent of the respondents buy in bulk because they do not like running out of stock. There are respondents who go out to shop out of urgency i.e. 34.3 percent. Some respondents also claimed that they go supermarkets to stay updated with different kinds of products that are new to the market.
6. The majority of the respondents have been using the e-commerce markets for more than five years i.e. 42.5 percent. While 24.6 percent and 27.5 percent have been using e-commerce for the last one year and less than a year respectively. This data indicates that the people in India are not very familiar with the technology.
7. The majority of the respondents i.e. 71 percent believe that the e-commerce is helpful to them as it provides a better platform for them to shop on. The other 22.2 percent believes that it helps in catering to the demands of the consumer. The minority of the respondents believe i.e. 6.8 percent believe that ensures the guarantee of the payment.
8. The majority of respondents i.e. 51.2 percent agree that e-commerce has its advantages over traditional commercial methods. The respondents who strongly agree to the notion is minor i.e. 5.3 percent. While there are respondents i.e. 33.8 who have a very neutral though about the statement.
9. The majority of the respondents i.e. 35.7 percent use e-commerce for banking while there are respondents i.e. 21.7 and 25.6 percent who use e-commerce for travel and tourism and stock exchange respectively.
10. The majority of the respondents i.e. 56 percent agree that e-commerce provides an alternative marketing channel by eliminating a middleman. While 16.9 percent strongly agree to the notion where as 18.8 percent feel neutral to the notion. The numbers of respondents who disagree to the notion are 8.3 percent.
11. The majority of respondents i.e. 34.8 percent do not use e-commerce because of lack of trust. While 23.7 percent and 28.5 percent of the respondents do not use because of awareness level is low and security concerns respectively.

5. SUGGESTIONS

1. It was found during the research that the consumers are not much familiar with the technology. Hence E-commerce companies marketing team should concentrate on improving the knowledge among the people who are not aware of the process.
2. Majority of the consumers believe that e-commerce is helpful to them in providing a better platform for them to shop on. So by providing introductory information to each and every customer that will help them to navigate around the website better.
3. During the survey it was found that the consumers are using the e-commerce platform for banking, travel and tourism, stock exchange, clothing and fashion accessories and daily usage items. For companies to achieve a high level of trust among these users, they should work on a very safe and secure pathway of transactions.

4. It was found in the survey that people are not aware about the online support system. So for the awareness of customers companies should create awareness for the consumers by the help of social media because it is more users friendly. Also asking for feedback will help them understand the areas in which they should improve in.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study mainly focuses on the factors that affect the consumer's E-Commerce behaviours. The young generation are more often purchasing from online sites because of the revolution in the technology among the young population and they are able to use this technology for their well-being more than other age group category. Flipkart and Amazon are the shopping sites which are more preferably used by the youngsters. There is an increasing demand for online shopping because of the variety of options for the consumers to choose and that to at a reasonable price. E-commerce is used by the consumers more for clothing & other fashion accessories rather than for other stuff such as electronics, matrimony and banking etc. There were a few factors that the study was focused on such as website, trust and privacy. Those factors were looked at and examined to reveal the influence at online consumer behaviours. Some old researches related to the topic were also used in order to understand and get clarity regarding the topic.

Moreover, the consumer's purchase decision making process was also examined to identify the potential factors. The information search is the most important factor that helps the customers find the suitable products or services for their needs. Therefore, online retailers need to enhance and improve the information supporting their product. This will provide more detailed product information and use internal search engine in order to increase the efficiency of information search. When a customer is prospecting the product, they would think more about the reputation of e-commerce website and payment security for the purchase stage. At the post purchase stage, the factors of after service which is most concerned about. Overall, the factors from internet that influenced or prevented online consumer behaviour need to be carefully concerned by the online retailers, who can utilize the appropriate marketing communications to support the customer's purchase decision making process and improve their performance.

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